

SELF-HANDICAPPING APPROACH: IMPLICATIONS ON LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT

By

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Abstract

Self-Handicapping has been examined as a self-protective strategy, used by adults; males and females in an attempt to externalize failure and internalizing success. As continuous as learning may seem when learners attribute their failure as a result of an excuse it tampers with their self-esteem thereby giving impression to self-handicap; this can affect their learning and development. It is a fact that learning and development of students is depleting as a result of fear of failure. The ability of success is threatened because of this phenomenon (Self-handicapping). The causes of self-handicapping are connected to low self-esteem, procrastination, self-impression, poor performance and many others. Thus, the paper examines self-handicapping approach: Implications on learning and development.

Keywords: Self-Handicapping, Learning, Development, learners

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Introduction

The study of self-handicapping had gone as far back 1970 in the areas of psychology, education, health, sports, amongst others. Education/training/learning is to human beings what water is to fish; every individual across spheres needs learning for survival as fish needs water for survival (Godwin, Ugochukwu, and Patience 2023). It is a fact that learning and development of students is depleting as a result of fear of failure. The ability of success is threatened because of this phenomenon. The causes of self-handicapping are connected to low self-esteem, procrastination, self-impression, poor performance amongst others. The effects of self-handicapping are evident in academia as low academic achievement, low self-esteem etc. the causes and effects of self-handicapping have promoted uncertainties which has led to the drop rate of student graduates, lack of employment, poor funding and lack of infrastructure.

Unfortunately, educational institutions has not done enough by providing framework for good facilities, improvement in teaching curriculum, training of manpower for development and many

others. This study holds that in order to cushion the effect of self-handicapping, prevention of self-handicapping must be understood by students, learners, teachers and instructors. Learning must be interactive and geared towards achieving academic success, sustenance, and personal development. Thus, the paper examines self-handicapping approach: implication to learning and development.

2.1 Concept of Self-handicapping

Self-handicapping is a self-destructive mechanism that an individual develops against his/her environment. According to Berglas and Jones 1978, originated and conceived self-handicapping, as a set of behaviour or claims primarily to protect one's self-image. Midgley and Urdan (1995), Garcia and Pintrich 1993 were among the first scholars interested in understanding how self-handicapping strategies are used in educational context. Litvinova (2015) sees self-handicapping as a paradoxical phenomenon-people creating barrier to protect one's perceived ability or self-esteem from failure and on the other side make the probability of failure more certain. There are two (2) variants to self-handicapping; claimed and behavioural self-handicapping. The latter involves reducing effort/creating obstacles as explanation while the former uses excuses to explain failure. These two variants of self-handicapping can be internal or external to the self-handicapper (Mitchell and Decker, 2017). The vicious cycle as described by Schwinger et al 2014 and Zuckerman et al., 1998) as a progression of self-handicapping is depicted in diagram shown below.

The ERO-spiral of self-handicapping (Schwinger et.al 2014 and Zuckerman et al., 1998)

According to Mitchell and Decker, (2017) explained the behavioural handicaps that adults engage in that affect learning and development viz- a-viz:

1. **Avoiding Accountability:** avoiding conflict and confrontation, making excuses or blaming others for failing.
2. **Tunnel Vision:** when face with difficult tasks avoidance sets in; thus tackling it becomes a problem and as such adult self-handicap

3. **Lack of Awareness:** little or no self-assessment of one's traits, strengths, or behavior
4. **Poor Analysis and Decision Making:** not asking the right questions, framing blindness in decision making, not knowing what you don't know, and not questioning yourself or your lecturers. Making decisions for instant gratification, impulse, selfishness, or to please others.
5. **Poor Communication Culture:** inability to create transparency and trust, not being consistent and open, lack listening skills, being defensive or unable to take constructive feedback, not allowing vulnerability or expression of doubt in classroom, and ignoring the wisdom of the lecturers/ peer-group.
6. **Poor Engagement:** viewing everything as a transaction, rather than as a partnership, not adding value to relationships, poor networking, talking about others behind their back, and aligning with only a few individuals (pack mentality).
7. **Poor Talent Development:** associating with the wrong people, not being on the lookout for colleagues who can sharpen skills, avoiding coaching, and mentoring, not paying attention to the fit of people in the classroom, and allowing coaching and mentoring from bad peers.
8. **Micro-managing:** studying through fear, coercion, and intimidation, constantly looking for fault and who to point fingers, being unable to cope with uncertainty or the unexpected, choosing situations where unexpected challenge or event will take place, and not understanding interpersonal boundaries.
9. **Not Driving for Results:** anything that keeps adults from focusing on outcomes – confusing effort with results, avoiding challenge and risk, spending time thinking about how things should be instead of taking action.

2.2 Correlates of Self-Handicapping

The correlates of self-handicapping includes; procrastination, academic stress, and perfectionism. This will be explained accordingly;

- I. **Procrastination:** this is an act of delaying or postponing a task. In a recent study, it was found that regular student compared with students who are special needs use procrastination- a state of behaving in contrast to one's best decision (Parwez et. al., 2023). Students often engage in academic procrastination by wasting time on idleness (gossip with colleagues, watching movies with friends, gossiping, playing computer games etc) when the time should have been spent on school related matters. Procrastination have significant effect on student grades, projects, as well as individual's life approximately, 25% to 75% of students delay academic work (Tibbett and Ferrari, 2015). As a result of procrastination students gives up on the completion of their program. This is caused by a number of cognitive distortions;
 - a) Exaggeration on how they are going to be in the future
 - b) Exaggeration on the timing to complete a task

- c) Wrong assumption on their right frame of mind to be able to finish a task/project
- d) Underestimating the duration for activities to be completed

Like self-handicapping, procrastination has negative psychological effect on learners. Result has found that procrastinators are faced with stress and sickness.

II. Academic/family Stress

Among the many stress situations students encounter, those involving academic stress seem to be the most frequent. Academic stress has become one of the most serious health issue in modern day world (Lu et al.,2003). When a learner have a negative perception to the extent that learning doesn't interest him, one may liken such learner to have undergone stress from his home environment. Stress has been seen as the reaction of learners to demands imposed on them. A situation where the well-being of learner is detrimentally affected by their failure to cope with the demands of academic work (Erkutlu and chafra, 2006). The interpersonal evaluation inherent in these situations is usually appraised as a threat to self-esteem. To cope with such threatening situations, learners attempt to present themselves in a particular way (self-handicapping). The negativity of stress has been long causing more harm than good ranging from psychological, physiological to health condition such as depression.

Outcome of Academic Stress

- **Unwanted behaviour:** such as low motivation, self-handicapping, absenteeism, low morale
- **Organisational cost:** cost of reduced performance/productivity, high replacement cost(increase in training, retraining, recruitment) compensation cost, sick-pay cost
- **Psychological effect:** anxiousness, impulsiveness, emotional fatigue, aggressiveness depression
- **Physiological effect:** headache, mental disorder, chronic pain, cardiovascular diseases, increased in blood pressure, increased in blood sugar, infections, insomnia
- **Organisational effect:** missing scholarship opportunities, low level of performance, losing grades.

III PERFECTIONISM

In every learning environment, learners are always evaluated of their performance(performance Evaluation) directly or indirectly. As the world of work becomes competitive and rewards are explicitly tied to achievement and good performance, promotion of self-protection strategies by learners are bound to set in (Martin et al.,2003). For adult not to be labelled as stupid, the struggle for competence set in. In these circumstances, perfectionist adult are particularly vulnerable so the moment they self-handicapped it gives an excellent alibi for poorer performance.

One characteristics of perfectionist is they strive flawlessly not to make mistakes, engaging in over activity, setting excessively high performance standard (Stoeber and Rennett, 2008; Appleton et al., 2009; Cumming and Duda, 2012) which is accompanied by tendencies for overly critical evaluation of one's behaviour (Frost, Marten, Lahart, and Rosenblate, 1990; Hewitt and Flett, 1991; Flett and Hewitt, 2002a).

Models of Perfectionism

Flett & Hewitt 1991 categorize perfectionism into;

- **Self-oriented perfectionism(S.O.P):** When adult learners set high personal standards, and evaluate their own performance against these standards they are said to be self-oriented perfectionists. They are often highly critical of their own work.
- **Other-oriented perfectionists (O.O.P):** it means learners who impose excessively high standards on others in their lives.
- **Socially proscribed perfectionists (SPP)** are those who perceive the significant of others hold excessively high standards for them. They experience anxiety, for they feel as though they must meet these high standards in order to please others.

Factors Influencing Perfectionism in Learners

There are factors that generates learners been perfectionistic. It can be seen as internal or external. It include; family influences, individual factors, fear of failure and causal attribution. They are further explained below;

- ❖ **Family influences:** when individual is experiencing maladaptive tendencies they focus their attention on other people's evaluation of their performance and they feel that their self-worth is contingent in meeting those expectation. Their believe is that unless they perform perfect they wont feel loved. For some learners, they adopt perfectionistic tendencies to please their family. The 2nd circumstances in which family influences on perfectionism is that such individual will learn that his family's love is contingent upon his successes he achieved. For instance, a student studying medicine to prove his/her perfectionism in front of immediate family members. Not minding the high expectation and high demand the discipline project; and still not meeting the standard expectation of the course but in as much they believe that it's the performance that makes them to be loved by their family the tendency of self-handicap set in.
- ❖ **Fear of failure:** prominent factor that underly a perfectionistic individual is fear of failure. Atkinson and Feather(1966) defined fear of failure as a disposition to avoid failure or capacity for experiencing shame or humiliation as a consequence of failure. In avoiding shame most adult have associated failure with aversive consequences as they perceived failure as threatening and experiencing fear and apprehension in evaluative situations (Conroy, Willow and Metzler,2002). By fear of failure individual cannot achieve competency as their failure will lead to set back thus providing an avenue to self-handicap and thereby affecting their performance.

- ❖ **Causal Attribution:** Attribution influences adult towards perfectionism. For instance self-oriented and socially proscribed perfectionist differs in the way they attributes for their successes and failure. Flett, Hewitt, Blankstein and Pickering(1998) assessed attribution on these dimensions (stability, locus of control, and controllability), the result found no correlation of these types of dimension on other-oriented perfectionism (O.O.P), but it was found that socially proscribed perfectionism was related to a learned-helplessness pattern of attribution. The self perfectionism(S.P) attributed positive and negative outcomes to external factors demonstrating a perceived lack of control and a tendency to blame others for the outcome of events.

Academic Context of Self-Handicapping: Implication for Learning

In academics, student use self-handicapping behaviour which are actual or fictitious obstacles or behavioural or verbal claims presented prior to engaging in activities such as exams test, oral presentation among others and which are used as plausible excuse for a potential failure (Gupta & Geetika, 2020, Jensen and Deemer, 2020, Boruchovitch et al., 2022). Teachers' attitude is directly linked and have impact on the educational experiences of students particularly among students with special needs hence they self-handicap (Maggio, 2020). Some theories have proved that negative attitudes towards special students predict negative behaviour, while positive attitude produce positive self-handicapping behaviour. A meta-analysis on academic self-handicapping and achievement, Schwinger et al., (2014) suggests that self-handicapping is maladaptive for academic performance. They posit a "vicious cycle" of low performance and self-handicapping that students enter into after singular handicapping situations. Students with self-handicapping behaviour experienced poor psychological health such as depression, anxiety, reduce self-esteem. These have adverse effect on academic performance, well-being and self-confidence, lower achievement, poor adjustment, and academic underachievement (Sahin, and Omur, 2020, and Adina, 2014).

Ways to reduce self-handicapping among learners

- Develop an attitude that will bring about confidence in any relative task being assigned to
- Prevention focussed orientation
- Autonomy support from social environment;family, organisation and family
- Group Cohesion
- Cognitive behavioural therapy: institution can bring intervention in form of coaching that can help learners who are handicapped and to bring it to bare minimum
- Positive self-talks
- Decreasing hyper-competitive environment

3.0 Conclusion

Learning is a life-long process, however, design of learning curriculum are cumbersome, tedious and stressful inhibiting adult learners success, and personal development. Howbeit, institutions, family, teachers and facilitators should not forget that learners are creatures of the moment,

perpetually immersed in the nitty gritty and are bound to make mistakes or exemplify some unwelcoming behaviours- such as self-handicapping. Hence, in order for institutions to achieve effectiveness and good service delivery, curriculum must be learners-friendly, teachers' attitude must be tailored towards learners success to enhance their personal development.

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